

“SOCIO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS AND CONSTRAINTS FACED BY BETEL LEAF GROWERS IN PRODUCTION AND MARKETING OF BETEL LEAVES IN BHOGRAI BLOCK, BALASORE, ODISHA”

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Abstract

The present study on socio-economic profile of the betel leaf growers was conducted in Bhograi block, Balasore district Odisha, the primary data were collected from 120 farmers from six villages. The study revealed that there were more male farmers than female. The study indicated that about 32.50 percent farmers earn less than Rs. 50,000 about 24.17 percent farmers earn Rs. 50,000 to 1 lakh about 29.15 percent farmers earn Rs. 1 lakh to 2 lakh and about 13.33 percent farmers earn more than Rs. 2 lakhs. Most of the farmers had agriculture occupation and most of the farmers were middle and old aged. Among the various constraints, fluctuation in market price was the first and foremost constraint faced by the betel vine growers and high cost of labour was the least constraint.

Key words: Socio-economic profile, Betel leaf growers, Different categories, Constraints in Production and Marketing

Introduction

Medicinal plants are very essential to human life. Most of the medicinal plants are wild and some are cultivated to increase the economy. Betel leaf is a medicinal, commercial and heritage crop, in which leaves of the plant is economically important. It is also known as ‘The Neglected Green Gold of India’. In India the leaves of betel vine are commonly called as Pan. This evergreen heart shaped leaf crop is widely recognised in Ayurveda for its medicinal properties such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic and it also acts as a mouth freshener. Betel vine (*Piper betel* L.), from family Piperaceae, is a shade loving, perennial, dioecious root climbers. The origin of betel vine is believed to be either from India, Sri Lanka, Malaysia and Indonesia. Betel leaf has many medicinal properties. It acts as a stimulant, it reduces inflammation, improves immunity, it has anti diabetic activity. In Odisha Betel vine is cultivated in coastal areas. Balasore, Bhadrak, Jagatsinghpur, Jajpur, Kendrapara, Puri, Cuttack and Ganjam are the betel leaf growing districts. From Odisha betel leaf is exported to Varanasi, Mumbai etc. Betel leaves are sold in Pana. One Pana contains 80 Koda. 1 Koda contains 50 leaves. After Covid Pandemic, it has been seen that farmers are not getting enough profit from betel vine cultivation. The current study focuses on the socio-economic profile and constraints faced by the betel leaf growers.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the socio-economic profile of the betel leaf growers in the study area.
2. To find out constraints and suggestions in production and marketing of betel leaves.

Research Methodology

Selection of District: In Odisha, there are 30 districts. Out of 30 districts Balasore, district was selected for the present study considering the large betel leaf production area.

Table-1: Socio Economic Profile of the Betel leaf growers

Sl. No.	Independent Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	101	84.10
		Female	19	15.84
2	Age	18-35 years (Young)	13	10.84
		36-55 years (Middle aged)	51	42.49
		More than 56 years (Old aged)	56	46.66
3	Education	Illiterate	17	14.17
		Functionally literate	15	12.5
		Primary	18	15.00
		Secondary	14	11.67
		Higher secondary	39	32.51
		College	17	14.17
4	Occupation	Agriculture	46	38.33

Selection of Block: A list of total blocks was obtained from the district head quarter. Of the total block in Balasore one block that is Bhograi block was selected purposively on the basis of large amount of production for current study.

Selection of Villages: A complete list of all villages was obtained from related Gram Panchayat office thereafter, villages were arranged in ascending order on the basis of area under betel leaves cultivation, and then Barbatia, Bhorai, Chauki, Gobindapur, Jalsuhuria, Nayagan, Neguan, Pasarbindhra, Sanausa, Suhuria villages were selected randomly on the basis of betel leaf production.

Selection of Farmers: A complete list of all betel leaf farmers was obtained from the gram Pradhan /head. These farmers were arranged in ascending order on the basis of their land holding, there after these farmers were categorized in five size farm group. Out of that 10% respondents were selected randomly on the basis of betel leaf cultivation for the study.

Analytical Tool

Percentage: $(X \div Y) * 100$

X= Number of respondents filling for the same category

Y= Total number of respondents

Garrett’s Ranking:

• It was used to find out the most significant factor which influences the respondent.

• As per this method, respondents had asked to assign the rank for all factors and the outcome of such ranking have been converted into score value with the help of the following formula:

$$\text{Percentage} = \frac{100 * (R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

• Where, R_{ij} = Rank given for ith item by jth individual

• N_j = No. of items ranked by jth individuals

Results And Discussion

		Agricultural labour	14	11.67
		Agriculture + Business	30	24.99
		Agriculture + Service	30	24.99
5	Annual Income	Less than Rs. 50,000	39	32.50
		Rs.50,000 to 1 lakh	29	24.17
		Rs. 1 lakh to 2 lakhs	25	29.15
		More than 2 lakhs	16	13.33

From table-1, it could be understood that 84.01 percent farmers were male and 15.84 percent farmers were female. Since most of the female were involved in managing their households, higher portion of the male participates in earning activities. While, only some of the female households take part in agriculture, as their male partners had other occupation. There were 10.84 percent farmers were young, 42.49 percent farmers were middle aged and 46.66 percent farmers were old aged. Since most of the young aged people were involved in white collar jobs and other business, most of the betel leaf growers were middle and old aged betel leaf growers. The study revealed 14.17 percent farmers were illiterate, 12.50 farmers were functionally

literate, 15.00 percent farmers were primary educated, 11.67 percent farmers were studied till secondary, 32.51 percent farmers were attained higher secondary and 14.17 percent college. It could be concluded that 38.33 percent farmers had agriculture occupation, 11.67 percent farmers were agricultural labour, 24.99 percent farmers had agriculture and business as their occupation and 24.99 percent farmers had agriculture and service as their occupation. The study indicated that about 32.50 percent farmers earn less than Rs. 50,000 about 24.17 percent farmers earn Rs. 50,000 to 1 lakh about 29.15 percent farmers earn Rs. 1 lakh to 2 lakh and about 13.33 percent farmers earn more than Rs. 2 lakhs.

Table-2: Calculation of Garret value and ranking of constraints experienced by betel leaf growers in production and marketing of betel leaves

Sl. No.	Statement	Score	Percent	Rank
1	Yield loss due to inconsistent climatic condition	6759	67.59	VII
2	Non availability of storage facilities	6460	64.6	VIII
3	Damage of leaves during transportation	6429	64.29	IX
4	High establishment cost	6255	62.55	X
5	Lack of adequate training	5278	52.78	XII
6	Lack of market information	5719	57.19	XI
7	Lack of availability of good planting material	4969	49.69	XIV
8	High cost of labour	4731	47.31	XV
9	Non availability of labour during the time of harvesting	5228	52.28	XIII
10	High cost for chemicals	7389	73.89	IV
11	Unavailability of credit	7124	71.24	V
12	Lack of price policy	7092	70.92	VI
13	Fluctuation in market prices	7834	78.34	I
14	High involvement of middlemen	7600	76	II
15	Lack of export options	7571	75.71	III

From table-2 it could be understood that various constraints encountered by the betel leaf growers in production and marketing of betel leaves. Among the various constraints, fluctuation in market price was the first and foremost constraint experienced by the betel vine growers, followed by high involvement of middlemen, lack of export options, high cost of chemicals, unavailability of credit, lack of price policy, yield losses due to inconsistent climatic condition, non-availability of storage facilities, damage of leaves during transportation, high establishment cost, lack of market information, lack of adequate training, non-availability of labour during the time, lack of availability of good planting material were the 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th, 10th, 11th, 12th, 13th and 14th constraint experienced by betel leaf growers respectively. Eventually, high cost of labour was the least experienced constraint faced by the betel leaf growers.

Conclusion:

There were more male farmers than female as most of the female were involved in managing their households, higher portion of the male participates in earning activities. While, only some of the female households take part in agriculture, as their male partners had other occupation. Since most of the young aged people were involved in white collar jobs and other business, most of the betel leaf growers were middle and old aged betel leaf growers. As most of the farmers want to continue their family occupation of agriculture, higher percentage of them were involved in agriculture. While, some of the farmers had other occupations based on their educational qualification as their primary occupation and supervise agricultural

activities. Majority of the farmers had annual income less than Rs. 50,000. To overcome the constraints we can encourage value added products, and can provide proper training to increase their knowledge about good quality input and for better farming.

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